

Supplementary Materials: Behavioral strategies of prehistoric and historic children from dental microwear texture analysis

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Statistical analyses

Table S3: Test for normality of dental microwear data

		<i>Statistic</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>epLsar</i>	Neandertal	0.934	0.549
	Early modern human	0.980	0.977
	Amarna	0.962	0.558
	Point Hope	0.870	0.225
<i>Asfc</i>	Neandertal	0.738	0.006
	Early modern human	0.834	0.014
	Amarna	0.527	<0.001
	Point Hope	0.890	0.319
<i>Smc</i>	Neandertal	0.633	<0.001
	Early modern human	0.475	<0.001
	Amarna	0.821	0.001
	Point Hope	0.840	0.131
<i>HAsfc9</i>	Neandertal	0.866	0.139
	Early modern human	0.942	0.448
	Amarna	0.892	0.024
	Point Hope	0.861	0.193
<i>HAsfc81</i>	Neandertal	0.927	0.486
	Early modern human	0.534	<0.001
	Amarna	0.960	0.510
	Point Hope	0.951	0.751